

Conference Abstract

Observations on Cetoniidae (Insecta: Coleoptera) from Madagascar

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Abstract

The Madagascan cetoniid fauna is very diverse and strongly endemic – with ca. 330 endemic species (mostly Stenotarsiini), due to the ancient isolation of Madagascar in respect to continental Africa. The principal taxonomic group of the Stenotarsiini does not occur outside the region. In this work, taxonomic and ecological observations and a checklist of the Cetonidae of Madagascar are provided.

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